

Analysis of the Local Lymph Node Assay (LLNA) variability for assessing the prediction of skin sensitisation potential and potency of chemicals with non-animal approaches

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 21 December 2015

Received in revised form 22 March 2016

Accepted 12 April 2016

Available online 13 April 2016

Keywords:

LLNA variability
Alternative methods
GHS/CLP
ECETOC
Validation

ABSTRACT

The knowledge of the biological mechanisms leading to the induction of skin sensitisation has favoured in recent years the development of alternative non-animal methods. During the formal validation process, results from the Local Lymph Node Assay (LLNA) are generally used as reference data to assess the predictive capacity of the non-animal tests. This study reports an analysis of the variability of the LLNA for a set of chemicals for which multiple studies are available and considers three hazard classification schemes: POS/NEG, GHS/CLP and ECETOC. As the type of vehicle used in a LLNA study is known to influence to some extent the results, two analyses were performed: considering the solvent used to test the chemicals and without considering the solvent. The results show that the number of discordant classifications increases when a chemical is tested in more than one solvent. Moreover, it can be concluded that study results leading to classification in the strongest classes (1A and EXT) seem to be more reliable than those in the weakest classes. This study highlights the importance of considering the variability of the reference data when evaluating non-animal tests.

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1. Introduction

The knowledge of the biological mechanisms leading to the induction of skin sensitisation has favoured in recent years the development of in chemico and in vitro test methods targeting key events of the skin sensitisation Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP; OECD 2012). Three of these methods, the Direct Peptide Reactivity Assay (DPRA), the KeratinoSens™ and the human Cell Line Activation Test (h-CLAT) underwent formal validation and independent peer-review (EURL ECVAM 2013; EURL ECVAM 2014; EURL ECVAM, 2015a). The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) adopted in 2015 the DPRA and the KeratinoSens™ as Test Guidelines (TG) 442C and 442D respectively (OECD 2015a; OECD 2015b), and a draft TG for the h-CLAT test method is in the final stages of the OECD adoption process. Within the TGs the validated test methods are proposed to support

the discrimination between skin sensitisers and non-sensitisers for the purpose of hazard classification according to the United Nations Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of chemicals (UN GHS; UN, 2015) and the European Union Regulation on Classification, Labelling and Packaging (EU CLP; European Commission, 2008). Besides these methods, a number of other assays are under development or evaluation (e.g. Johansson and Lindstedt, 2014; Reisinger et al., 2015). It is a commonly held view that the inherent limitations of the available methods, including the limited mechanistic coverage of the biological events leading to the acquisition of skin sensitisation, impede their use in isolation as full replacements of the currently used animal tests. For this reason, it is envisaged that only a combination of methods used in the context of Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) will be able in the short term to replace the usage of animals for regulatory purposes. An IATA can be defined as an approach based on multiple information sources used for the hazard identification, hazard characterisation and/or safety assessment of chemicals. An IATA integrates and weights all relevant existing data, and guides the targeted generation of new data, where required, to inform regulatory decision-making regarding potential hazard and/or risk.

Progress has been made in recent years in the development of defined approaches to testing and assessment for skin sensitisation based on a fixed set of information sources, e.g. in silico, in chemico

Abbreviations: ACE, acetone; AOO, acetone:olive oil (4:1 by volume); DMF, dimethylformamide; EC3, effective concentration inducing a stimulation index of 3; ETOH/DEP, Ethanol/diethylphthalate; EXT, extreme (ECETOC classification); IDR, Insufficient Dose Response; MOD, moderate (ECETOC classification); NEG, negative; SI, stimulation index; TG, Test Guideline; TMPTA, ethyl-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediol triacrylate.

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and in vitro methods, in which the final prediction is derived from the integration and interpretation of data from the various sources also in a fixed, defined way. The OECD is currently working on the development of guidance on how to report such defined approaches proposed to be used within IATA with specific emphasis on those developed in the skin sensitisation area (Draft OECD Document – not yet publicly available). As in the case of individual test methods, defined approaches to testing and assessment are considered with respect to their accuracy in correctly predicting the in vivo response.

Among the animal tests, the Local Lymph Node Assay (LLNA) is generally used as the gold standard against which the performance of alternative methods is compared (e.g. Piroird et al., 2015; Urbisch et al., 2015). The LLNA provides quantitative information on sensitisation potency expressed as an EC3 value (i.e. the concentration of test chemical required to induce a 3-fold increase in lymph node cell proliferation) allowing also the evaluation of concentration-response information from in chemico and in vitro methods. During the formal validation of non-animal testing methods, test chemicals for which the in vivo response is less uncertain are selected, for example by selecting those with LLNA positive or negative classifications that are consistent with other in vivo responses (i.e. data from guinea-pig test or human data) (Casati et al., 2009; EURL ECVAM, 2012; EURL ECVAM, 2015b). Thus, the variability of the LLNA data (or other in vivo reference data) and its impact on the assessment of alternative methods are usually not explicitly addressed in validation activities. The emphasis is rather on establishing a balanced validation set comprising substances with different physicochemical properties, sensitisation potency, reaction mechanisms and diverse structures. However, when evaluating the predictive capacity of the defined approaches, generally many more chemicals are used and therefore the criteria used in the chemicals selection for the validation study are no longer feasible to use. Thus, there will certainly be chemicals with dubious in vivo data in this particular case and therefore the uncertainty associated with the reference data increases.

Knowledge of the variability of the in vivo reference method would allow for a more quantitative assessment of non-animal methods and defined approaches to testing and assessment. In fact, several toxicological investigations have shown the value of conducting an analysis of reference method variability (Adriaens et al., 2014; Hoffmann, 2015; Barroso et al., 2016).

This study reports a statistical analysis of published available LLNA data in order to characterise the inherent variability of the LLNA for both hazard assessment (sensitisers versus non-sensitisers) and sensitisation potency categorisation. Since the type of vehicle used in a LLNA study is known to influence to some extent the EC3 value (Basketter et al., 2001; Jowsey et al., 2008; Anderson et al., 2011) our analysis was first performed by considering chemicals that have been tested more than once with the same vehicle. This first analysis (referred to hereafter as “solvent considered”) allowed us to characterise the biological component of LLNA assay variability, since the contribution of the vehicle was removed. However, in practice, when multiple LLNA results are available for a given chemical, the studies have often been performed with different vehicles making it difficult to identify which study results are more relevant for the purpose of evaluating non-animal methods. For this reason, the analysis of LLNA variability was also performed by considering all studies for a given chemical irrespective of the vehicle used. This second analysis (referred to hereafter as “solvent not considered”) allowed us to characterise the overall (biological and vehicle-related) variability of the LLNA.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data sources

The evaluation of the LLNA variability was performed using the National Toxicology Program Interagency Centre for the Evaluation of

Alternative Toxicological Methods (NICEATM) LLNA Database (niceatm-llnadatabase-23dec2013.xls), which is publicly available at: <http://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/results/dbsearch/index.html#NICEATM-LLNA-Database>. This database pools data from published and unpublished data sources with permission and comprises 669 chemicals and a total of 1060 entries (i.e. 1060 LLNA studies). Each chemical is identified by name, CAS number, molecular weight and chemical class. Each entry reports the details of one LLNA study: the concentrations tested (%), the stimulation index (SI) for each concentration, the EC3 value (%) for positive chemicals (or NC for negative results), the LLNA result (positive – POS or negative – NEG) and the original reference. For some positive chemicals, the dose-response observed in the experiment was insufficient to calculate an EC3 value; in such cases the abbreviation IDR (Insufficient Dose Response) is reported instead of the EC3 value.

For the purpose of this study, the NICEATM LLNA database was supplemented with LLNA data retrieved from: 1) Basketter et al. (2014): this paper reports EC3 values for 105 chemicals, but the solvent used in each study is not specified in the publication; 2) Piroird et al. (2015): this paper includes a database of 175 chemicals, reporting EC3 values for each chemical; 3) Urbisch et al. (2015): this paper presents a database of 213 chemicals, reporting the EC3 values for each chemical and the original references; 4) the QSAR Toolbox (available at: <http://www.qsartoolbox.org/>). From these three last data sources, and when it was possible, the solvent used to test the chemical was retrieved from the original reference.

All the identified LLNA study duplicates were removed for the purpose of the analysis.

2.2. Analysis of the data

2.2.1. Selection of chemicals

For the analysis of variability considering the potential solvent effect (“solvent considered”), studies were grouped on the basis of the CAS number of the tested chemical and the solvent used for testing.

For the analysis of variability without taking into consideration the solvent effect (“solvent not considered”), studies were grouped according to the CAS number of the tested chemical, regardless of the solvent used for testing.

In both cases, all the chemicals with at least two studies were retrieved from the final database and used for the analysis.

2.2.2. Classification of LLNA studies

For the purpose of the analysis, LLNA studies were classified as positive/negative (POS/NEG) according to the classification criteria in the OECD TG 429 (OECD, 2009), where an LLNA study is considered as positive if the SI at any tested dose is ≥ 3 . In addition, for substances identified as positive in the LLNA, the GHS/CLP hazard sub-categorisation criteria for distinguishing between Category 1A (strong skin sensitisers and substances showing high potency in animals) and Category 1B (other sensitisers and substances showing low to moderate potency in animals) were applied (Table 1). Moreover, the four potency categories: weak (WEAK), moderate (MOD), strong (STRONG) and extreme (EXT),

Table 1
GHS/CLP and ECETOC potency classification based on EC3 values derived from the LLNA.

Potency class	EC3 (%) cut-off values		
<i>GHS/CLP classification</i>			
1A			≤ 2
1B	> 2	–	
<i>ECETOC classification</i>			
Extreme			< 0.1
Strong	≥ 0.1	–	< 1
Moderate	≥ 1	–	< 10
Weak	≥ 10	–	≤ 100

Table 2
GHS/CLP classification scheme: examples of grouping and distribution of normalised studies.

Chemicals (solvent)	Number of studies with NEG result	Number of studies with Category 1B result	Number of studies with Category 1A result	Assignment to groups ^a	Study distribution according to classes	Distribution of the normalised studies in the different classes ^{b,c}
Glycerol (DMF)	2	0	0	NEG group	2/2 studies → NEG 0/2 studies → 1B 0/2 studies → 1A	NEG group: NEG = 1 /1B = 0/1A = 0
Atrazine (ACE)	2	2	0	NEG & 1B groups	2/4 studies → NEG 2/4 studies → 1B 0/4 studies → 1A	NEG group: NEG = 0.5 /1B = 0.5/1A = 0 1B group: NEG = 0.5/ 1B = 0.5 /1A = 0
Benzocaine (DMF)	5	1	1	NEG, 1B & 1A groups	5/7 studies → NEG 1/7 studies → 1B 1/7 studies → 1A	NEG group: NEG = 0.72 /1B = 0.14/1A = 0.14 1B group: NEG = 0.72/ 1B = 0.14 /1A = 0.14 1A group: NEG = 0.72/1B = 0.14/ 1A = 0.14

^a Chemicals with discordant studies are represented in more than one group.

^b In the analyses, the final weight of each chemical in each group to which it is assigned is always 1, being equal to the sum of the scores of the normalised studies.

^c The text in bold indicates the proportion of classifications matching the group designation (e.g., the proportion of 1B classifications in the 1B group).

proposed by the European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals (ECETOC, 2003) were considered (Table 1).

For the purpose of the analysis, each chemical was assigned to a group (i.e. POS or NEG for POS/NEG classification scheme; NEG, 1B or 1A for GHS/CLP classification scheme; NEG, WEAK, MOD, STRONG or EXT for ECETOC classification scheme) on the basis of having at least one study resulting in a classification matching that group. Chemicals with discordant studies are therefore represented in more than one group. Then, within each group, the multiple studies available for each chemical were distributed in the corresponding relevant classification/potency classes (Table 2). Since the chemicals analysed have a variable number of repeat studies available (ranging from 2 to 40 for the study “solvent considered” and from 2 to 46 for the study “solvent not considered”), each study was normalised to the total number of studies available for that chemical, i.e. the number of studies assigned to a specific class for a given chemical was divided by the total number of studies available for that chemical (Table 2). In this way, each chemical contributes with a final weight of 1 in all analyses performed.

Table 2 illustrates how the LLNA studies for three chemicals glycerol (2 studies), atrazine (4 studies) and benzocaine (7 studies) were assigned to the different groups and classes on the basis of the classification criteria described in Table 1 and the normalisation of the studies described above.

2.2.3. Number of chemicals used for the analysis

The LLNA database used for the analysis reports results for 87 chemicals (400 studies) that were eligible for the “solvent considered” analysis and for 93 chemicals (518 studies) that were eligible for the “solvent not considered” analysis. Two reasons explain the difference in numbers: 1) some chemicals had multiple studies but only a single study for a given solvent; this type of study was not included in the analysis “solvent considered” but was included in the analysis “solvent not considered”; and 2) the database was supplemented with chemicals for which the solvent used was not reported in the original reference, these chemicals were included only in the “solvent not considered” analysis.

Among the 87 chemicals used for the “solvent considered” analysis, 85 were eligible for the GHS/CLP and the ECETOC classifications. Two chemicals were removed from the GHS/CLP and ECETOC analyses since only one study qualified – in the second study the dose-response was not sufficient to derive an EC3 value and was therefore labelled as IDR. Nevertheless, the studies labelled as IDR were included in the POS/NEG analysis, being attributed to the POS class. For the “solvent not considered” analysis, among the 93 chemicals with multiple study

results, 87 were eligible for the GHS/CLP and ECETOC analyses. Six chemicals were removed for the same reason explained above.

3. Results

3.1. Distribution of chemicals with concordant and discordant results

First, data were analysed on the basis of whether the repeat studies available for each chemical, and conducted using the same solvent, yielded concordant or discordant results for the classification scheme considered (Fig. 1). For the three different classifications schemes considered in our analysis, approximately 10% of the chemicals have concordant negative studies. As expected, the number of chemicals with discordant studies increases with the number of classes considered: 22% for the POS/NEG classification (2 classes), 38% for the GHS/CLP classification (3 classes) and 52% for ECETOC classification (5 classes).

A similar evaluation was performed without considering the solvent used in the studies available for each chemical (Fig. 2). In this case, only around 5% of the chemicals show concordant negative studies (irrespective of the classification scheme). As before, the percentage of chemicals with discordant study results increases with the number of classes considered: 32% for POS/NEG, 51% for the GHS/CLP classification and 61% for the ECETOC classification.

3.2. LLNA EC3 value variability

The EC3 values (expressed as % concentration) reported for each study were used to analyse the inherent variability of the LLNA. The mean of the logarithmically (decimal) transformed EC3 values available for each chemical and the standard deviation (SD) were plotted on a graph with the chemicals ordered by increasing EC3 mean. Studies for which an EC3 value was not available in the database (i.e. NEG and IDR) were also included on the graph even though they did not contribute to the calculation of the mean EC3 and SD. Figs. 3 and 4 show the variability of the EC3 values when the solvent effect is considered, and not considered, respectively. The chemicals used for both analyses provide a good coverage of skin sensitisation potency and distribution in all the classes of the GHS/CLP and ECETOC classification schemes. Figs. 3 and 4 show that the variability of the LLNA is more or less consistent throughout the sensitising potency scale and doesn't seem to correlate with a specific potency class.

Concerning the “solvent considered” analysis (Fig. 3), the highest variability in EC3 values (SD of Log EC3 values >0.5) was observed, in decreasing order of variability, for oxalic acid when tested in dimethylformamide (DMF); tetramethylthiuram disulphide tested in

Fig. 1. Distribution of chemicals with concordant/discordant study results in the “solvent considered” analysis. A: POS/NEG classification; B: GHS/CLP classification; chemicals with concordant positive studies were assigned to the corresponding sub-category 1B or 1A; C: ECETOC classification; chemicals with concordant positive studies were assigned to the corresponding potency class WEAK, MOD, STRONG or EXT.

Fig. 2. Distribution of chemicals with concordant/discordant study results in the “solvent not considered” analysis. A: POS/NEG classification; B: GHS/CLP classification; chemicals with concordant positive studies were assigned to the corresponding sub-category 1B or 1A; C: ECETOC classification; chemicals with concordant positive studies were assigned to the corresponding potency class WEAK, MOD, STRONG or EXT.

4:1 acetone:olive oil (AOO); trimellitic anhydride tested in AOO; phenyl benzoate tested in AOO; ethyl-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediol triacrylate (TMPTA) tested in acetone (ACE); 4-phenylenediamine tested in AOO; 1,2-benzisothiazolin-3-one tested in DMF; jasmine absolute tested in 1:3 ethanol/diethylphthalate (EHOH/DEP); aniline tested in AOO; and benzoyl peroxide tested in ACE. As a result of the highly variable LLNA results for these 10 chemicals no specific potency class can be assigned with 100% confidence.

Concerning the “solvent not considered” analysis (Fig. 4), the highest variability in EC3 values (SD of Log EC3 values >0.5) was observed, in decreasing order of variability, for oxalic acid; trimellitic anhydride; tetramethylthiuram disulphide; benzoyl peroxide; diphenylcyclopropanone; TMPTA; formaldehyde; glutaraldehyde; 4-phenylenediamine; 1,2-benzisothiazolin-3-one; phenyl benzoate; jasmine absolute; and 2,4-dinitrobenzene sulfonic acid. As a result of the highly variable LLNA results for these 13 chemicals, no specific potency class can be assigned with 100% confidence.

Finally, it is worth noting that LLNA negative results were obtained even for chemicals showing extreme or strong sensitising results ($EC3 \leq 2\%$; $\text{Log } EC3 \leq 0.3$) in repeat studies both in the “solvent considered” analysis shown in Fig. 3 (e.g. cobalt chloride tested in DMSO, tetramethylthiuram disulphide tested in AOO, 1,4-dihydroquinone tested in acetone/saline (1:1)) and in the “solvent not considered” analysis shown in Fig. 4 (e.g. benzalkonium chloride, potassium dichromate, 1,4-

dihydroquinone). Also for these chemicals it may be difficult to assign a potency class with 100% confidence.

3.3. Distribution of LLNA studies in different classes

The analysis of the distribution of LLNA studies is presented in Table 3. To avoid bias in the analysis due to the different numbers of repeat studies available for each chemical ($n = 2$ to 40 for the “solvent considered” analysis and $n = 2$ to 46 for the “solvent not considered” analysis), the studies were normalised as described in the **Materials and methods** section. The percentage of studies in each class was then calculated by dividing the sum of the scores of the normalised studies assigned to that class by the total number of chemicals in the group.

It is worth noting that irrespective of the classification scheme the number of chemicals with negative LLNA studies is almost the same, i.e. 28 for the “solvent considered” analysis and 35 for the “solvent not considered” analysis. Among these chemicals, 19 out of 28 (68%) and 30 out of 35 (86%) in the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses, respectively, have studies with discordant results.

3.3.1. POS/NEG classification scheme

The “solvent considered” analysis shows that 19 out of 78 (24%) chemicals in the POS group give discordant study results, which is

Fig. 3. Analysis of the inherent variability of the LLNA considering the solvent. Data are presented as Mean \pm SD of log-transformed EC3 values ($n = 87$) for chemicals ordered by increasing mean EC3 value and considering the solvent used to test the chemical (“solvent considered”). The number associated with each error bar reports the number of experiments with an EC3 value and used for the calculation of the mean and SD. The symbol \times and \blacklozenge respectively indicate that at least one IDR or at least one NEG result is available for that chemical in the database. The numbers associated with these symbols represent the number of IDR or NEG studies. The grey dotted line represents the GHS/CLP classification cut-off; the black dotted lines represent the ECETOC classification cut-offs.

almost 3 times lower than in the NEG group (Table 3). Consequently, when considering all chemicals, in the NEG group only 65% of the studies classify the chemical as negative whereas in the POS group 88% of the studies classify the chemicals as positive (Table 3). In other words, the probability that a negative study, if repeated, would lead to a positive classification is as high as 35%, compared to a probability of only 12% for obtaining a negative result when repeating a positive study. There is therefore considerably higher certainty in a POS result obtained with a single LLNA study than in a single study with a NEG result.

When the analysis is performed without considering the solvent, the proportion of chemicals with discordant study results increases for both groups: 30 out of 35 (86%) for the NEG group and 30 out of 88 (34%) for the POS group (Table 3). Also in this case the results for all chemicals demonstrate that there is higher certainty in a POS result obtained with a single LLNA study (85% probability of obtaining again a positive result in a repeat study) than in a single study with a NEG result (51% probability of obtaining again a negative result in a repeat study).

3.3.2. GHS/CLP classification scheme

When considering GHS/CLP, for the 19 chemicals with discordant studies assigned to the NEG group in the “solvent considered” analysis, 34% and 16% of the studies classify the chemicals as Category 1B and Category 1A, respectively, with the remaining 50% being NEG.

Considering all the chemicals, 66% of the studies identify the chemicals as NEG, 23% as Category 1B, and 11% as Category 1A. As expected, the percentage of studies classifying the chemicals as NEG decreases between the analysis for all chemicals and the one for only the chemicals with discordant studies, while increasing for Category 1B and remaining roughly the same for Category 1A (Table 3). Similarly, the percentage of studies identifying the chemicals as NEG decreases when the analysis is performed not considering the solvent (Table 3).

In the 1B group when considering the solvent, 28 out of 50 (56%) chemicals have studies with discordant results. Less than 50% of those studies classify the chemicals “correctly” as Category 1B (43%), with the rest identifying them evenly as NEG (29%) or Category 1A (28%). Without considering the solvent, the proportion of chemicals with discordant studies increases slightly (39 out of 65; 60%). Similarly to what observed in the analysis performed considering the solvent, 50% of the experiments classify the chemicals as Category 1B (46%), with a roughly equal distribution of the remaining studies between a NEG (30%) and a Category 1A (24%) outcome. Finally, taking into account the 50 chemicals in the 1B group (including those with discordant as well as those with concordant studies), 68% of the studies identified the chemicals as Category 1B (in both the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses), with the rest identifying them evenly as NEG (16–18%) or Category 1A (14–16%) (Table 3).

Fig. 4. Analysis of the inherent variability of the LLNA not considering the solvent. Data are presented as Mean \pm SD of log-transformed EC3 values ($n = 93$) for chemicals ordered by increasing mean EC3 value and without considering the solvent used to test the chemical (“solvent not considered”). The number associated with each error bar reports the number of experiments with an EC3 value and used for the calculation of the mean and SD. The symbol \times and \blacklozenge respectively indicate that at least one IDR or at least one NEG result is available for that chemical in the database. The numbers associated with these symbols represent the number of IDR or NEG studies. The grey dotted line represents the GHS/CLP classification cut-off; the black dotted lines represent the ECETOC classification cut-offs.

In the 1A group, 19 out of 41 (46%) chemicals in the “solvent considered” analysis have studies with discordant results, with this proportion increasing (24 out of 36 chemicals; 67%) when the solvent was not considered. In both analyses, about half of those studies classified the chemicals as Category 1A (53–55%), while 32–34% identified the same chemicals as Category 1B and 13% as being NEG. The study distribution for all chemicals shows that 79% (“solvent considered”) and 69% (“solvent not considered”) of the studies classify the chemicals as Category 1A. Accordingly, the proportions of Category 1B (15–23%) and NEG (6–8%) studies decrease to nearly half of what is observed for only the chemicals with discordant studies (Table 3).

3.3.3. ECETOC classification scheme

Focusing on the discordant chemicals, it can be observed that only 50% of the studies identify the chemicals as NEG. The other half of the studies assigns the chemicals to the WEAK (17%), MOD (23%), STRONG (8%) or EXT (2%) classes (Table 3). When looking at the distribution of the studies for all the chemicals assigned to the NEG group in the “solvent considered” analysis, 34% of the studies identify the chemicals as skin sensitizers (12% WEAK, 16% MOD, 5% STRONG and 1% EXT). When the solvent is not considered, the pattern of study distribution for all chemicals and for discordant chemicals remains the same as when solvents are considered, with the percentage of studies identifying the chemicals as NEG decreasing and the proportions of all other classes increasing.

In the WEAK group, 22 out of 29 (76%) or 26 out of 37 (70%) chemicals have discordant studies in the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses, respectively. Less than half of the discordant studies classify the chemicals as WEAK (45–47%), with the majority of the remaining studies identifying the chemicals with only one class difference (15–24% NEG and 27–36% MOD). Considering the study distribution for all chemicals in the WEAK group, about 40% of the studies identify the chemicals as being other than WEAK (in both the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses), with the majority of these studies again being either NEG (11–17%) or MOD (19–28%). The pattern of distribution of the studies does not vary much between the “solvent considered” and the “solvent not considered” analyses.

In the MOD group, 32 out of 40 (80%) or 36 out of 46 (78%) chemicals have discordant studies in the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses, respectively. Like in the WEAK group, less than half of the discordant studies classify the chemicals as MOD (45–47%) but, in this case, the majority of the remaining studies identify the chemicals as either WEAK (19–24%) or NEG (18–19%), i.e. with up to two classes difference. Considering the study distribution for all chemicals in the MOD group, 57% of the studies identify the chemicals as being MOD (in both the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses), with the majority of the remaining studies again identifying the chemicals with up to two classes difference (15% NEG and 15–19% WEAK). The pattern of distribution of the studies also

Table 3
Distribution of LLNA studies according to the three classification schemes. The first values correspond to the “solvent considered” analysis; values in brackets correspond to the “solvent not considered” analysis.

POS/NEG classification												
	Total no of chemicals ^a	No of chemicals with discordant studies	Study distribution for chemicals with discordant studies (%)		Study distribution for all chemicals (%)							
			NEG class	POS class	NEG class POS class							
NEG group	28 (35)	19 (30)	49 (43)	51 (57)	65 (51) 35 (49)							
POS group	78 (88)	19 (30)			12 (15) 88 (85)							
GHS/CLP classification												
	Total no of chemicals ^a	No of chemicals with discordant studies	Study distribution for chemicals with discordant studies (%)			Study distribution for all chemicals (%)						
			NEG class	1B class	1A class	NEG class 1B class 1A class						
NEG group	28 (35)	19 (30)	50 (44)	34 (41)	16 (15)	66 (52) 23 (35) 11 (13)						
1B group	50 (65)	28 (39)	29 (30)	43 (46)	28 (24)	16 (18) 68 (68) 16 (14)						
1A group	41 (36)	19 (24)	13 (13)	32 (34)	55 (53)	6 (8) 15 (23) 79 (69)						
ECETOC classification												
	Total no of chemicals ^a	No of chemicals with discordant studies	Study distribution chemicals with discordant results (%)					Study distribution for all chemicals (%)				
			NEG class	WEAK class	MOD class	STRONG class	EXT class	NEG class	WEAK class	MOD class	STRONG class	EXT class
NEG group	28 (35)	19 (30)	50 (44)	17 (20)	23 (24)	8 (9)	2 (3)	66 (52)	12 (17)	16 (20)	5 (8)	1 (3)
WEAK group	29 (37)	22 (26)	15 (24)	47 (45)	36 (27)	0 (3)	2 (1)	11 (17)	60 (61)	28 (19)	0 (2)	1 (1)
MOD group	40 (46)	32 (36)	18 (19)	24 (19)	47 (45)	9 (13)	2 (4)	15 (15)	19 (15)	57 (57)	7 (10)	2 (3)
STRONG group	20 (19)	13 (18)	6 (7)	0 (2)	27 (30)	45 (41)	22 (20)	4 (6)	0 (2)	17 (29)	64 (44)	15 (19)
EXT group	17 (16)	7 (9)	1 (8)	5 (4)	6 (8)	42 (31)	46 (49)	1 (4)	2 (2)	2 (5)	17 (18)	78 (71)

^a The number of chemicals in each group (shown in the second column) is determined on the basis of the number of chemicals in the database having at least one study resulting in a classification matching that group. Consequently, chemicals with discordant studies are represented in more than one group (see explanatory Table 2).

does not vary much between the “solvent considered” and the “solvent not considered” analyses.

In the STRONG group, 13 out of 20 (65%) or 18 out of 19 (95%) chemicals have discordant studies in the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses, respectively. Less than half of these discordant studies classify the chemicals as STRONG (41–45%), with the majority of the remaining studies identifying the chemicals with only one class difference (27–30% MOD and 20–22% EXT). Six to 7% of the studies give a NEG outcome. Considering the study distribution for all chemicals in the STRONG group, 64% or 44% of the studies identify the chemicals as STRONG in the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses, respectively. Again, the majority of the remaining studies were identified with up to one class difference, i.e. either MOD (17–29%) or EXT (15–19%). For the STRONG group, the study distribution varies between the “solvent considered” and the “solvent not considered” analyses when considering all chemicals (i.e., a considerably lower percentage of STRONG studies in the “solvent not considered” analysis), but not when considering only the discordant chemicals. This is because only 1 chemical out of 19 has concordant studies if the solvent is not considered versus 7 out of 20 if the solvent is considered (Table 3).

Finally, in the EXT group 7 out of 17 (41%) or 9 out of 16 (56%) chemicals have discordant studies in the “solvent considered” and “solvent not considered” analyses, respectively. About half of the discordant studies classify the chemicals as EXT (46–49%), with the majority of the remaining studies identifying the chemicals as STRONG (31–42%). Considering the study distribution for all chemicals in the EXT group, 71–78% of the studies identify the chemicals as EXT with most of the remaining studies identifying the chemicals as STRONG (17–18%). Importantly, even in this EXT group, 1–4% of the studies give a NEG result (Table 3).

4. Discussion

The potential of a chemical to induce allergic contact hypersensitivity is an integral part of hazard assessment in the regulatory context. In recent years, the LLNA has become the preferred method for skin sensitisation because of animal welfare benefits (compared with other animal models) and because it provides dose-response information from which the relative sensitisation potency of a chemical can be derived and used for safety assessment. However, important progress has been made in the development of non-animal methods for skin sensitisation testing due to the good understanding of the chemical and biological basis of this toxicological effect, as documented in the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) for skin sensitisation (OECD, 2012). Some of these methods have recently been adopted by the OECD (OECD, 2015a; OECD, 2015b), and another one (h-CLAT) is at the final stage in the adoption process. Other methods are currently undergoing evaluation in ring-trials (e.g. Gibbs et al., 2013; Johansson et al., 2014; Cottrez et al., 2015; Ramirez et al., 2016). The available test methods are measuring specific mechanisms of the skin sensitisation pathway and as such, they are not generally proposed as stand-alone full replacement methods. Activities are under way to understand how these methods can be used in defined approaches in the context of IATA in order to replace animal testing for both hazard and risk assessment purposes (e.g. Bauch et al., 2012; Jaworska et al., 2013; Nukada et al., 2013; Maxwell et al., 2014; van der Veen et al., 2014; Hirota et al., 2015; Jaworska et al., 2015; Natsch et al., 2015; Urbisch et al., 2015; Takenouchi et al., 2015; Asturiol et al., submitted for publication).

Although the available methods represent individual pieces of the puzzle, their predictive power has generally been evaluated in terms of prediction of in vivo responses due to the lack of reference data for the key events they are in fact measuring. LLNA data are predominantly

used as the benchmark for the evaluation of new alternative methods and/or defined approaches. During formal validation studies, attention is paid to select chemicals for which the reference *in vivo* data are relatively certain with regard to their skin sensitisation potential or lack thereof (Casati et al., 2009; EURL ECVAM, 2013; EURL ECVAM 2014; EURL ECVAM 2015a) to accurately judge the performance of the non-animal methods under evaluation. The variability of the reference data is rarely taken explicitly into account. However, many more chemicals are generally used to evaluate the predictive capacity of defined approaches to testing and assessment. In this case, the inclusion of test chemicals with more uncertain reference data can no longer be avoided, and the overall uncertainty associated with the reference data obviously increases. It is therefore important to understand how reliable the reference data are, not only for judging non-animal methods/approaches providing information on the potential skin sensitisation hazard but also for methods/approaches aiming at potency prediction.

None of the animal and non-animal toxicity tests is perfect, and this includes the LLNA whose strengths and limitations have been extensively described in the scientific literature (Basketter et al., 2002; Jowsey et al., 2008; Anderson et al., 2011). It is therefore important to keep in mind the limitations of the reference data when using them for assessing the performance of new test methods and of their combinations in defined approaches to testing and assessment, which cannot be expected to be more accurate in predicting the reference data than the reference method is predictive of itself (i.e. the reproducibility of the reference method).

The objective of the study presented in this paper is to provide a picture of the variability of the LLNA for a set of chemicals for which multiple studies are available. The LLNA variability analysis was performed taking into consideration three classification schemes: the positive/negative classification (POS/NEG), the GHS/CLP classification which subcategorises sensitisers in subcategories 1A (strong sensitisers) and 1B (others than strong sensitisers), and the ECETOC classification with four potency classes (WEAK, MODERATE, STRONG and EXTREME).

In the LLNA, the vehicle used to solubilise the test chemicals is known to have an impact on the relative potency (i.e. the EC3 value) of skin sensitising chemicals (Basketter et al., 2001; Jowsey et al., 2008; Anderson et al., 2011; Hoffmann, 2015). Therefore, the analysis was conducted by considering LLNA studies performed with the same vehicle. In practice, in the presence of multiple LLNA studies performed with different vehicles for the same chemical, it is difficult to select which studies are more relevant for the purpose of evaluating non-animal methods. For this reason, the analysis of LLNA variability was also performed without taking into consideration the solvent used.

In a recent analysis published by Hoffmann (2015) the variability of the LLNA assay was analysed using data reported in the NICEATM database. The ECETOC classification accounting for 5 potency classes was the one considered for the purpose of the study and the chemicals were assigned to a potency class on the basis of the median EC3 values. Our analysis is based on a different approach since it focused on the distribution of individual LLNA study results. The analysis was performed not only for the ECETOC classification scheme but also for the dichotomous POS/NEG and the GHS/CLP classification schemes. Our work therefore complements the analysis performed by Hoffmann (2015).

The number of chemicals with discordant study results increases with the number of classes considered. This number also increases when the solvent effect is not taken into account (Figs. 1 and 2). For example, for the dichotomous hazard classification scheme (POS/NEG) and when the solvent is considered, 22% of the chemicals have discordant study results. When the solvent is not taken into account, the percentage of chemicals with discordant studies increases to 32%.

Considering the POS/NEG classification scheme, LLNA studies resulting in negative classifications tend to be less reliable than studies with positive classifications. When considering the solvent, there is a

35% chance that studies with negative results would lead to a positive result if repeated. When the solvent is not considered the probability of obtaining discordant results between LLNA studies increases to 50%.

The analysis of the LLNA studies distribution for the different classification schemes (Table 3) shows that the POS, 1A and EXT groups have a lower percentage of chemicals with discordant studies than other groups. In fact, with the exception of these three groups, this proportion is always above 50%. Considering the “study distribution for all chemicals”, the highest concordance is also observed for the positive and strongest potency groups: POS (85–88%), 1A (69–79%) and EXT (71–78%). For the other groups, the percentage of studies classifying the chemicals to the same class is on average 64% for the “solvent considered” analysis and 55% for the “solvent not considered” analysis.

For the GHS/CLP classification scheme and considering the NEG and the 1A groups, the majority of the discordant studies were assigned to the adjacent class 1B (Table 3). In the intermediate group 1B, an equal proportion of the studies assigns the chemicals as NEG or 1A. For the ECETOC classification scheme, considering the NEG group, the results show that most of the discordant studies were almost evenly assigned to the MOD and WEAK classes. In the WEAK and EXT groups, the discordant studies are mostly in the adjacent classes (MOD and STRONG, respectively). The MOD group on the other hand shows that most of the discordant studies were evenly distributed in the less severe WEAK and NEG potency classes. Finally, the discordant results of the STRONG group show an almost equal distribution between the two adjacent classes of lower (MOD) and higher (EXT) potency. On the basis of this analysis it is difficult to identify a clear pattern for the distribution of the discordant studies leading to a less or more severe classification. Of note is also the fact that even in the EXT group, 1 to 4% of the studies gave a NEG result.

A second analysis was performed without considering the solvent used when testing the chemicals. Except for the WEAK and MOD groups in the ECETOC classification scheme and the 1B group in the GHS/CLP classification scheme, by not considering the solvent the proportion of discordant studies increases. The highest proportion of discordant studies is for the NEG class for all three classification schemes, the 1A class for GHS/CLP, and the STRONG class for ECETOC. If only the discordant chemicals are considered, the pattern of distribution is almost the same as when the solvent is considered.

This study highlights the importance of considering the variability of the LLNA when this assay is used as the standard against which to compare the performance of alternative methods. Considering the POS/NEG classification scheme, LLNA studies resulting in negative classifications tend to be less reliable than studies with positive classifications. When potency classification is considered (i.e. GHS/CLP and ECETOC) study results leading to classifications in the strongest potency classes (1A and EXT) seem to be more reliable than those in the weakest classes. As already observed by Hoffmann (2015), studies with discordant classifications mainly classify the chemical in an adjacent class, but it does not appear possible to draw general conclusions on whether such studies lead to a more severe or less severe classification.

Considering the current discussion at regulatory level on the acceptance of results from *in vitro* methods and their use within defined approaches, it would be important, for a given regulatory application, to discuss and agree on the level of accuracy required for acceptance of defined approaches based on the use of non-animal data. The definition of such a level should be informed by the uncertainty associated with the reference data. In the case of non-animal methods for skin sensitisation, acceptable levels of accuracy for different classification schemes can be derived from the results presented in Table 3. For example, a level of accuracy for identifying NEG, 1B and 1A chemicals of 70%, 70% and 80%, respectively, would be comparable to the performance of the LLNA based on our most conservative analysis (i.e. best LLNA performance) conducted by considering the solvent.

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